

Horizontal and vertical transmission of microsporidia *Nosema pyrausta* and *Nosema bombycis* in the predatory bug *Podisus maculiventris* (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae)

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Abstract

Predatory insects play an important role in the regulation of arthropod's numbers. When they counteract with the diseased prey, the entomopathogenic microorganisms may be disseminated mechanically or parasitize such secondary hosts. Microsporidia are wide-spread pathogens of insects with diverse host ranges, and infection of entomophagous hosts is not uncommon. In the present study, the spined soldier bug nymphs were fed with the adzuki bean borer larvae infected with *Nosema pyrausta* (A. Paillot) J. Weiser, 1961 or the silkworm larvae infected with *N. bombycis* Nägeli, 1857. Both pathogens were infective to the predator at the prevalence level of 15–30%. The former pathogen displayed a decrease of prevalence level in the filial generation to as low as 5 % and no infection in consequent generations. The latter could only be transmitted to bugs horizontally and no infections in the filial generation was found. This indicates low (or no) risk of vertical transmission of these two pathogens, making them suitable for combined application with the predatory bug in the integrated pest management programmes.

Keywords

Parasite-host interactions, infection persistence, insect pathogens, biocontrol, integrated pest management

Introduction

Pest management is important for agriculture as well as human health (Kevan et al. 2020). Extensive application of synthetic pesticides leads to environmental pollution and food contamination (Geiger et al. 2010; Tang et al. 2021; Dwivedi et al. 2022; de Azeredo Morgado et al. 2023), as well as the development of pest resistance which requires increased application rates, active compound rotation, novel delivery approaches etc. (Cross 2013; Biddinger et al. 2014; Godfray and Garnett 2014; Sparks and Nauen 2015; Kudsk et al. 2018; Möhring 2020). Even though modern chemical pest control means can be safe when all application regulations are respected (Dolzhenko and Laptiev 2021), the insecticides might be applied under suboptimal conditions. Examples of such situations include unsuitable abiotic factors (Amarasekare and Edelson 2004; Sreelakshmi 2021) and inappropriate developmental stages of the pests (Vivan et al. 2017; Stejskal et al. 2021), forcing the farmers to increase dosage and frequency of insecticide application remarkably. For these reasons, alternative means of pest control, including natural enemies, are of great importance. Entomopathogenic microorganisms are able to persist in pest populations, causing either acute infections that provide relatively quick death, or chronic diseases that affect the viability of pests with a transgenerational effect (Lewis et al. 2006; Solter et al. 2012; Litwin et al. 2020). Entomophagous arthropods are a significant component of terrestrial ecosystems. The use of predatory insects of various orders as biological means of plant protection plays an important role regulating arthropod's numbers (de Castro et al. 2015; Lin et al. 2021).

Predatory insects can act as mechanical carriers of insect pathogens. A lot of works is devoted to the study of the ability of predatory insects to spread nuclear polyhedrosis viruses through the excretion of infective particles with feces. Insect pests swallow occlusion bodies when eating infected plant parts. Predatory insects *Hippodamia convergens* Guérin-Méneville, 1842 (Pell and Vandenberg 2002), *Orius laevigatus* (Fieber, 1860) (Down et al. 2009), *Oechalia schellenbergii* (Guérin-Méneville, 1831) (Cooper 1981), *Podisus maculiventris* (Say, 1832) (Biever et al. 1982; Abbas and Boucias 1984), *P. nigrispinus* (Dallas, 1851) (Carvalho et al. 2012), *Eo-canthecona furcellata* (Wolff, 1811) (Gupta et al. 2013) are considered the most effective in the spread of entomopathogenic fungi, bacteria, and viruses.

Non-target predatory insect species are often used as a targeted spread of entomopathogens directly in the phytophagous population – spread of the fungus *Pandora neoaphidis* (Remaud. & Hennebert) Humber, 1989 by the seven-spotted ladybeetle *Coccinella septempunctata* Linnaeus, 1758 entomopathogenic for *Acyrtosiphon pisum* (Harris, 1776) and *Sitobion avenae* (Fabricius, 1775) (Roy et

al. 2001), distribution conidium *Cordyceps fumosorosea* (Wize) Kepler, B. Shrestha & Spatafora, 2017 by the ladybeetle *H. convergens* to control the Russian wheat aphid *Diuraphis noxia* (Mordvilko, 1913) (Pell and Vandenberg 2002), transfer of the entomopathogen *Lecanicillium longisporum* (Petch) Zare & Gams, 2001 from the common ant *Lasius niger* (Linnaeus, 1758) to rosy apple aphid *Dysaphis plantaginea* (Passerini, 1860) (Bird et al. 2004), the use of predatory insects *Harmonia axyridis* (Pallas, 1773) and *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens, 1836) in the distribution of *Beauveria bassiana* (Balsamo-Crivelli) Vuillemin s.l., 1912 to control green peach aphid *Myzus persicae* (Sulzer, 1776) (Zhu and Kim 2012).

However, the widespread use of entomopathogens complicates the system of interactions and leads to unpredictable effects that require special studies (Haddi et al. 2020; Mansour and Biondi 2021). The assessment of possible negative effects of entomopathogens on predators is of main importance in these studies, since their antagonism impairs the effectiveness of integrated plant protection (Sedaratian et al. 2014). From the predator's perspective, many pathogens and parasites reduce the energy value of prey, reducing predator survival and reproduction (Thieltges et al. 2013; Hatcher et al. 2014; Flick et al. 2016). So, the predatory bug *P. nigrispinus* unable to live more than three generations by consuming only virus-infected of the nuclear polyhedrosis virus (NPV) of the velvetbean caterpillar, *Anticarsia gemmatalis* Hübner, 1818 (AgNPV) (de Nardo et al. 2001). Knowledge about the impact of various groups of entomopathogens on predatory insects needs to be expanded (Sedaratian-Jahromi 2021).

The spined soldier bug *P. maculiventris* is used as an effective biological pest control agent. For example, *P. maculiventris* is effective against *Leptinotarsa decemlineata* (Say, 1824) (Hare 1990) and *Pieris brassicae* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Stamopoulos and Chloridis 1994; Aldrich and Cantelo 1999), *Heliothis virescens* Fabricius, 1777 and *H. zea* (Boddie, 1850) (López et al. 1976), *Spodoptera exigua* (Hübner, 1808) (De Clercq and Degheele 1994), *Pyrrhalta viburni* (Paykull, 1799) (Desurmont and Weston 2008), and many others. So, in addition to direct predation, the *P. maculiventris* is also capable of spreading such entomopathogens as *Lacania oleracea granulovirus* (LoGV) and *Microsporidium necatrix* (J.P. Kramer) V. Sprague, 1977 microsporidia, infecting *Lacania oleracea* (L., 1758) and *S. littoralis* (Boisduval, 1833). However, the lifespan and egg production of *P. maculiventris* are significantly reduced after ingestion of caterpillars infected with the microsporidium *M. necatrix* (Down et al. 2004). When selecting infected *B. bassiana* compared to uninfected cutworm larvae *S. frugiperda* J.E. Smith, 1797 nymphs of predatory bugs more often chose uninfected individuals and avoided infection with an entomopathogen (Avery et al. 2022). However, *P. maculiventris* is not always effective and it is possible to consider methods of its effectiveness as a biological control agent (De Clercq 2000).

Predatory insects, when spreading pathogens such as microsporidia in phytophagous prey's populations, contribute to the persistence of pathogens and further reduce the number of pests. The ability for many species of microsporidia to infect

insects of various families and orders is described (Tokarev et al. 2016; Malysh et al. 2018). This is especially pronounced in close and constant contacts, which are observed, in particular, in parasitic insects that infect Coleoptera (Saito and Bjørnson 2013), Diptera (Futerman et al. 2006), Hymenoptera (Schuld 1999) and Lepidoptera (Simões 2015). Microsporidia spores are spread both from an infected host to a susceptible host, with faeces, through decomposing tissues, through cannibalistic feeding (horizontal transmission) (Brooks 1988; Becnel and Andreadis 1999; Campbell et al. 2007; Saito and Bjørnson 2006; Goertz and Hoch 2008; Goertz and Hoch 2011; Wang-Peng et al. 2018) and from parental to filial generation (vertical transmission) (Becnel and Andreadis 1999; van Frankenhuyzen et al. 2007; Han and Watanabe 1998; Grushevaya et al. 2021). So, Wang-Peng et al. (2018) found that healthy individuals of the migratory locust *Locusta migratoria* (Linnaeus, 1758) can become infected with *Antonospora locustae* (E.U. Canning) C.H. Slamovits, B.A.P. Williams & P.J. Keeling, 2004 microsporidia by eating food contaminated with the predatory insect's feces. Moreover, microsporidia *A. locustae* is able to survive among migratory locusts' populations for several years. Predators of migratory locusts are able to acquire large numbers of spores while consuming the infected specimens. Marti & Hamm (1985) showed that spores of an unidentified *Vairimorpha* sp. remained intact in the intestines of the big-eyed bug *Geocoris punctipes* (Say, 1832) after ingesting infected tissues from *S. frugiperda* larvae. It has been determined that *G. punctipes* can be a potential vector for spreading pathogenic spores of *Vairimorpha* sp. Goertz and Hoch studied the influence of the forest caterpillar hunter *Calosoma sycophanta* (Linnaeus, 1758) on the interaction between its prey *Lymantria dispar* Linnaeus, 1758 and two microsporidia species *Vairimorpha lymantriae* (J. Weiser) Kunimi, 1993 and *V. disparis* Vávra J., Hylíš M., Vossbrinck C.R., Pilarska D.K., Linde A., Weiser J., McManus M.L., Hoch G. & Solter L.F., 2006 that infect the phytophagous insect. *V. lymantriae* and *V. disparis* spores were spread by predatory insects by consuming the infected caterpillars. When spreading spores by *C. sycophanta*, 45% to 69% of the caterpillars tested were infected (Goertz and Hoch 2013). Spores of microsporidia *V. necatrix* and *Pleistophora* sp. (extracted from *S. frugiperda* and the *Pleistophora* sp. from *Dasychira basiflava* Packard, 1864, respectively) are able to remain infective after passing through the digestive tract of the bug *Zelus exsanguis* Stål, 1862. However, none of the tested bugs was infected with microsporidia (Kaya 1979).

The present work aimed to study the possibility of microsporidia commonly found in lepidopteran hosts to infect a predatory bug and to persist in a row of subsequent generations under lab conditions. Our main hypothesis is that the broad host range of microsporidia of the genus *Nosema* allows for successful infection of a predator belonging to another insect order, such as the spined soldier bug *P. maculiventris*, feeding on heavily infected prey (horizontal transmission). Another question under investigation is whether this infection can persist through the generations of the new host (vertical transmission).

Materials and methods

Insect cultures and their pathogens

The adzuki bean borer and *Nosema pyrausta*

Diapausing last instar larvae of the adzuki bean borer *Ostrinia scapularis* (Walker, 1859) were collected from the stalks of the common cocklebur of *Xanthium strumarium* L., 1753 in Slavyansky District of Krasnodar Area in April 2021 and were transported to St. Petersburg. The whole life cycle was maintained at +24 °C using a meridic diet for larval feeding (Frolov et al. 2019).

The culture of the adzuki bean borer was maintained in the same facility and manipulated by the same operator as the European corn borer *O. nubilalis* Hübner, 1796 culture. The latter originated from a field population described elsewhere (Grushevaya et al. 2021) which turned out to be naturally infected with the microsporidium *N. pyrausta* (Paillot) Weiser, 1961. As a result, the *O. scapularis* culture became occasionally contaminated with the microsporidium and the next generation of the insect was subsequently infected at the rate of about 30 %. Thus, the *N. pyrausta*-infected larvae were utilized for feeding and respective infection of *P. maculiventris* (see below).

The silkworm and *Nosema bombycis*

The silkworm eggs were acquired from the Stavropol sericulture station (Pyatigorsk) and propagated in the laboratory. The mulberry leaves grown at the facilities of All-Russian Institute of Plant Protection were used to feed the larvae *Bombyx mori* (Linnaeus, 1758). The *N. bombycis* Nägeli, 1857 spores were obtained from the Scientific Research Institute of Sericulture (Tashkent, Uzbekistan) and kept as a refrigerated water suspension for one month prior to the experiments. The experimental infection was performed by feeding *N. bombycis* spores to the third instar *B. mori* larvae at the dosage of 10⁴ spores/larva, spore suspension smeared against the mulberry leaflet fed to the insects. After complete consumption of the infective dosage, the larvae were maintained at the same conditions for three weeks, fed with fresh mulberry leaves. The presumably infected larvae, as well as the control ones, were exposed to *P. maculiventris* (see below).

The spined soldier bug

The spined soldier bug is maintained in a permanent laboratory culture at the facilities of All-Russian Institute of Plant Protection in a separate building where experimental handling of the pathogens is excluded. The last instar larvae and newly emerged pupae of the mealworm *Tenebrio molitor* Linnaeus, 1758 were used as the feed source for nymphs and adults (De Clercq et al. 1998).

Experimental infection of the spined soldier bug

Horizontal transmission test

Either fifth instar larvae of *O. scapularis* or third instar larvae of *B. mori* were placed individually in glass Petri dishes, 20 cm in diameter. As many as five one-day old feed-deprived second instar nymphs of *P. maculiventris* were placed per dish. The bugs attacked the larvae and collective feeding of nymphs was observed (Fig. 1). After 48 hours, the cadavers of prey larvae were removed for analysis (see below, section 2.3). A moistened piece of cotton and fresh feed insects as above were provided to the bugs for the rest of the experiment. The bugs were reared until molting to the adult stage and used for vertical transmission test (section 2.2.1). To test for horizontal transmission, presence of microsporidia was examined in larval and adult cadavers (section 2.3).

Vertical transmission test

After molting to adult, the pairs of bugs (one male and one female) obtained within each variant, referred to as parental generation (P_0), were placed into separate glass Petri dishes for mating and oviposition. For vertical transmission test, their offspring, referred to as filial generation (F_1) was routinely maintained in glass Petri dishes until the adult stage. Then the new adult bug pairs were formed to obtain the consequent second filial generation (F_2) in the variants where the microsporidian infection tended to persist. Those bugs initially reared on microsporidia-free larvae of both *O. scapularis* and *B. mori* (in the assays using *N. pyrausta* and *N. bombycis*, respectively) were utilized as the control in the parental generation, as well as in consequent filial generations to ensure absence of cross-contamination during the whole experiment.

Diagnostics of microsporidia in insects

Prior to the experiments, the specimens from the stock cultures of Lepidoptera and the spined soldier bug were checked using light microscopy to ensure they are free from the microsporidia infections. After the larvae of Lepidoptera were exposed for bug feeding, they were dissected and smears were prepared from the inner tissues. Similarly, the cadavers of the adult bugs were dissected for light microscopy. Smears of inner tissues were examined by bright field light microscopy using Carl Zeiss Axio 10 Imager M1 at 400x magnification. The intensity of infection was estimated basing upon the number of spores per microscope field at 400x magnification, counted at 10 different spots of the smear: light (1-10 spores per field), mediocre (10–100 spores) and heavy (over 100 spores). The remaining parts of microsporidia-positive specimens were frozen for consequent molecular detection.

For genomic DNA extraction we used a simplified protocol of Sambrook et al. (1998) without addition of phenol. Insect tissues were homogenized with a plastic pestle in 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes in 100 μ l lysis buffer CTAB. After homogenization, 500 μ l lysis buffer with 0.2 % β -mercaptoethanol was added to the samples and incubated for 2 hrs at + 65°C. DNA was further extracted with chloroform and isoamyl alcohol (24:1), precipitated with isopropanol and washed with 70 % and 90% ethanol. Dried DNA pellets were resuspended in 50 μ l of ultra-purified water. The primers 18f/1047r specific to the locus of SSU rRNA were used to obtain fragments ~900 bp. The PCR mix consisted of 4 μ l of DNA, 5 μ l of DreamTaq Green PCR Master Mix, and 0.5 μ l of primers (forward and reverse). The PCR conditions: initial denaturation (95°C for 5 min), 35 amplification cycles (denaturation at 95°C for 1min; annealing at 54°C for 1 min, elongation at 72°C for 1 min) and a final extension step (72°C for 5 min). The amplicons were visualized using electrophoresis in 1 % agarose gels with GeneRuler Ladder Mix molecular weight marker (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The cut sections of the gel were melted in a 3 M solution of guanidine isothiocyanate, and the amplicons were purified by the silica sorption method (Vogelstein and Gillespie 1979).

The purified amplicons were sequenced in forward direction according to Sanger (Sanger et al. 1977) using an ABI Prism sequencer by Evrogen, Moscow, corrected manually in BioEdit and compared with Genbank entries using BLAST utility. Genbank (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide/>) was used to extract nucleotide sequence data for SSU rRNA gene of *N. bombycis* and *N. pyrausta*. The nucleotide sequences were aligned in BioEdit (Hall 1999).

Figure 1. Collective feeding of *Podisus maculiventris* second instar larvae utilizing lepidopteran larvae: (A) fifth instar larva of *Ostrinia scapularis* infected with *Nosema pyrausta*; (B) third instar larva of *Bombyx mori* infected with *Nosema bombycis*.

Statistical analysis

The exact Fisher test (Fisher 1992) to compare the infection prevalence levels between the variants. The main goal was to evaluate the differences between the variants of the parental bugs fed with the control and microsporidia-infected prey larvae, as well as between the parental and the filial generations within each variant.

Results

Experiments with *Nosema pyrausta*

Cultivation of the microsporidia-free *O. scapulalis* culture in one facility with the temporary *N. pyrausta*-infected culture of *O. nubilalis* resulted in contamination of the healthy culture. Out of 34 *O. scapulalis* larvae assayed, 8 specimens turned out to be heavily infected with microsporidia spore masses, corresponding to the 23.5 ± 7.3 % infection. When the infected insects were exposed to the groups of 5 second instar nymphs of *P. maculiventris*, they were eagerly attacked within the first 12 hrs and perished within 48 hrs since exposure. The groups of nymphs which fed on the infected adzuki bean borer larvae were chosen for further rearing until the adult stage. The 25 adult bugs that survived in the parental generation (P_0) were subjected to post-mortem analysis. Microsporidia spores of shape and size characteristic of *N. pyrausta* were observed in adipose tissue and silk glands of 4 specimens, corresponding to 16.0 ± 7.3 % mean prevalence level. This value was significantly different from the uninfected control group, as inferred from the results of the exact Fisher test (Table 1). To determine species allocation of the microsporidium observed in the predator tissues, SSU rRNA gene fragment was sequenced, showing 100 % identity to the homologous sequence of *N. pyrausta* available under Genbank accession # HM566196.

The intensity of infection was high, comparable to that of the primary insect host (Fig. 2). The progeny of these infected females was further reared as the first filial generation (F_1) using only microsporidia-free feed insects. Consequently, the second (F_2) and the third (F_3) filial generations were acquired. Among 116 F_1 bugs reared till adult stage, as many as 6 specimens were microsporidia-positive, showing multiple parasite spores in the smears prepared from the whole body homogenates or separate samples of fat body, muscles, Malpighian tubules and salivary glands. This corresponds to $5,17 \pm 2,06$ % prevalence level, which is about three times as low as in the parental generation, though these values are not significantly different. The intensity of infection varied from mediocre to heavy. However, F_2 and F_3 bugs turned out to be uninfected. As for the control, no microsporidia infection was detected both in the parental generation (Table 1) and subsequent filial generations (not shown).

Table 1. Prevalence levels of *Nosema pyrausta* in parental generation (P₀) of *Podisus maculiventris* primarily fed with the infected *Ostrinia scapularis* larvae and their respective progeny of first (F₁), second (F₂) and third (F₃) filial generations

Variants	Infective dosage, spores/larva	Generation	Sample size, pcs	Samples identified as infected ± SE	
				Pcs	%
Control	–	P ₀	75	0	0 ^{aA}
<i>Nosema pyrausta</i>	Spontaneous infection	P ₀	25	4	17.39 ± 7.90 ^{bB}
		F ₁	116	6	5.17 ± 2.06 ^b
		F ₂	43	0	0 ^a
		F ₃	42	0	0 ^a

Figure 2. Spores of *Nosema pyrausta* on smears prepared from infected insect tissues: (A) *Ostrinia scapularis*, magnification ×400, scale bar = 20 μm; (B) *Ostrinia scapularis*, magnification ×1000, scale bar = 10 μm; (C) *Podisus maculiventris*, magnification ×400, scale bar = 20 μm; (D) *Podisus maculiventris*, magnification ×1000, scale bar = 10 μm.

Experiments with *Nosema bombycis*

Out of 10 silkworm larvae fed with *N. bombycis* at the dosage of 10^4 spores/larva, only one turned out to be free from the infection. The other nine specimens had their inner tissues heavily loaded with the spores. Only those bugs fed with the infected larvae were considered for the experiment. Among those 43 bugs reared till adulthood, there were 12 specimens showing microsporidian spores (Fig. 3) with light to heavy infection intensity, thus constituting $27,91 \pm 6,84$ % prevalence level, statistically significant as compared to the control. However, among 83 bugs of the filial generation, none was infected.

Similarly, all the 15 silkworm larvae fed with *N. bombycis* at the dosage of 10^4 spores/larva became infected and among 73 P_0 bugs, the infection with mediocre to heavy intensity was found in 12 bugs, i.e. $15,07 \pm 4,19$ %, again significantly different from the control. Just like in case of *N. pyrausta*, the infected tissues were the adipose tissue and salivary glands. Their filial generation was also not infected, just like the control (Table 2). Sequencing the diagnostic fragment of SSU rRNA gene in microsporidia-positive bugs showed 100 % identity with the homologous sequence of *N. bombycis* (#D85503).

Figure 3. Spores of *Nosema bombycis* on smears prepared from infected insect tissues: (A) *Bombyx mori*, magnification $\times 400$, scale bar = 20 μm ; (B) *Bombyx mori*, magnification $\times 1000$, scale bar = 10 μm ; (C) *Podisus maculiventris*, magnification $\times 400$, scale bar = 20 μm ; (D) *Podisus maculiventris*, magnification $\times 1000$, scale bar = 10 μm .

Table 2. Prevalence levels of *Nosema bombycis* in parental generation (P₀) of *Podisus maculiventris* primarily fed with the infected *Ostrinia nubilalis* larvae and their respective progeny of first (F₁), second (F₂) and third (F₃) filial generations

Variants	Infective dosage, spores/larva	Generation	Sample size, pcs	Samples identified as infected ± SE	
				Pcs	%
Control	–	P ₀	75	0	0 ^A
<i>Nosema bombycis</i>	10 ⁴	P ₀	43	12	27.91 ± 6.84 ^B
		F ₁	84	0	0 ^A
	10 ⁵	P ₀	73	11	15.07 ± 4.19 ^B
		F ₁	175	0	0 ^A

Discussion

Many species of microsporidia are highly contagious to their insect hosts and cause intensive infections both in nature and during artificial cultivation under conditions of laboratory and industrial rearing (van Frankenhuyzen et al. 2004; Babin et al. 2022). *N. pyrausta* is not an exception. In field, the infection prevalence rates typically average at the level of 5–10 % in Europe (Malysh et al. 2011; Grushevaya et al. 2018) but is higher by an order of magnitude in North America (Lewis et al. 2006). In the laboratory, experimental infection even with low dosages, such as 10⁴ spores/larva, results in infection levels exceeding 90 % in both type host (Grushevaya et al. 2020) and other vulnerable pyraloid moths, such as the beet webworm *Loxostege sticticalis* Linnaeus, 1761 (Malysh et al. 2018).

The same applies to *N. bombycis*, which is widespread in nature, infecting wild populations of various butterfly species (Tokarev et al. 2020), not to mention of extensive epizootics occurring in captive industrial cultures of the main host *B. mori* (Chakrabarty et al. 2013). It is therefore expected that predatory insects may encounter high loads of microsporidian spores while feeding on lepidopteran larvae. Infections of entomophagous insects with the host-derived microsporidia have been documented repeatedly (see Introduction).

The dosages of *N. bombycis* spores utilized for experimental infection of silkworm larvae are variable. In the study of transovarial transmission of *N. bombycis*, 50 third instar larvae were fed a diet containing 1.8×10⁴ spores/cm³ and only 19 specimens survived to moth stage with 15 % infection level, while higher dosages caused negligible or zero moth survival (Han and Watanabe 1998). In the studies of the effects of gut commensal bacteria supplementation on larval susceptibility to the microsporidium, the dosages used ranged between 25 and 2.5×10⁷ spores per larva (Suraporn and Terenius 2021; Zhang et al. 2022). Similarly, to study the mid-gut response of silkworm larvae to infection at the level of differentially expressed

genes, the dosages of 2×10^3 (Li et al. 2018) and 2×10^4 spores/larva (Ma et al. 2013) were applied. Thus, the parasite load exploited in the present work is in the range of dosages routinely applied in experimental studies to induce massive infection of inner tissues of the host.

To our mind, the exposure of the heavily infected phytophagous insects to the predator is an appropriate model of possible natural interactions to test susceptibility of the predator to microsporidia in their prey at the maximally available level. It perfectly shows that even high loads of the pathogens are not causing epizootics in the predator under conditions of artificial rearing and same should be expected in nature.

Interestingly, even though *N. bombycis* and *N. pyrausta* display different host ranges when assayed against a series of lepidopteran species (Tokarev et al. 2020), both were able to infect the spined soldier bug at similar levels via the horizontal transmission route. This serves as another example of host switching of microsporidia (Malysh et al. 2018; Saito and Bjørnson 2013; Futerman et al. 2006; Schuld 1999), explaining the broad distribution of these parasites in insects and other invertebrate, as well as vertebrate hosts.

Infection of entomophagous arthropods can be beneficial for the pathogen dissemination in the primary phytophagous insect host populations and transmission to the new pest species, but possible adverse effects cannot be ruled out when intensive infections are developed in the predatory and parasitic insects.

In another study, *N. pyrausta* did not affect the fertility and lifespan of the common green lacewing *C. carnea*. Throughout the development of this host, swallowed spores remained in the intestinal lumen of the predatory insect and were excreted with feces. As a result, these spores did not infect the predator's tissues, but remained infective for the corn borer larvae (Sajap and Lewis 1989). Similarly, other species of microsporidia from phytophagous prey did not adversely affect predatory insects, as the infection of their inner tissues was not established (Kaya 1979; Smirnov and Eichhorn 1970; Young and Hamm 1985). The predators therefore only participated in spreading of the entomopathogens through defecation (Cooper 1981; Kaya 1979; Young and Hamm 1985; Capinera and Barbosa 1975). Interestingly, similar observations were made when an insect microsporidium *N. ceranae* Fries I., Feng F., da Silva A., Slemenda S.B. & Pieniasek N.J., 1996 was exposed to an insectivorous vertebrate, the bee eater *Merops apiaster* Linnaeus, 1758. The feces of this bird, which feeds on honey bees, contained spores of the microsporidium originating from, and retaining infectivity to, this insect host (Valera et al. 2011). Participation of the Lepidoptera-associated microsporidia in natural trophic webs and their virulence to the predators under the conditions of horizontal and vertical transmission is of great importance both for ecosystem balance and application of biocontrol agents. In the present study, horizontal transmission was observed for the two microsporidia species when the predator fed on prey intensively infected with the microparasites. The prevalence range of infections developed in the horizontally infected bugs was be-

low 30 %. Presence of the spore masses in infected bugs suggests possibility of further horizontal dissemination of the infection because cannibalism is widespread among the representatives of the genus *Podisus* (De Clercq and Degheele 1992). Yet, low levels of horizontally transmitted infection from the primary host to the predator suggests that further spreading within the predator's populations will be even less intensive.

Another principal route of dissemination of microsporidia is via vertical transmission from the parental generation to the filial one, ensuring and seasonal progress of infection (Zimmermann et al. 2016) and long-term persistence in populations of particular species over time (Siegel et al. 1988). In case of *P. maculiventris*, however, it can be concluded that the microsporidia from the lepidopteran insects are not well suited for efficient vertical transmission in the non-specific heteropteran host. This is well supported by the in diminishing prevalence rates of *N. pyrausta* in the row of consequent generations in the present study. Moreover, absence of *N. bombycis* infection in the filial generation of the bug ensures safety of this pathogen from the standpoint. This indicates low risk of vertical transmission of these two pathogens, making them suitable for combined application with the predatory bug in the biological and integrated pest management programmes.

Conclusion

It is vitally important to understand how biocontrol agents of different groups counteract when applied simultaneously. In the present study, two microsporidia from lepidopteran insects showed low levels of persistence in the predatory bug. *N. pyrausta* was able to infect the bug directly and their progeny at a diminishing rate. Meanwhile, *N. bombycis* could only infect the bug directly with no transmission to the progeny. Thus, these microsporidian species pose little risk to the spined soldier bug which is widely utilized for plant protection.

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